

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

for

Multi-class plant hormone HILIC-MS/MS analysis coupled with high-throughput phenotyping to investigate plant-environment interactions

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Tab. S1:

A complete list of analytes used in the current work.

No. in Fig.2	Compound	Analyte abbreviation	Internal standard	Biological role
1	melatonin	MLT	D4-MLT	Plant hormone like properties
2	indole-3-acetamide	IAM	D6-iPR	IAA metabolism
3	oxophytodienoic acid	OPDA	D4-SA	Active compound, JA precursor
4	salicylic acid	SA	D4-SA	Active compound
5	isopentenyladenine	iP	D6-iP	Active compound
6	isopentenyladenosine	iPR	D6-iPR	iP precursor
7	indole-3-butyric acid	IBA	D6-iPR	IAA precursor
8	jasmonic acid	JA	D5-JA	JA-Ile precursor
9	phenylpyruvic acid	PPyA	D6-ABA	PAA metabolism (putative)
10	abscisic acid	ABA	D6-ABA	Active compound
11	abscisic acid glucose ester	ABA-GE	D6-ABA	ABA metabolism
12	<i>cis</i> -zeatin	cZ	15N4-cZ	Active compound
13	<i>trans</i> -zeatin	tZ	D5-tZ	Active compound
14	indole-3-acetic acid	IAA	13C6-IAA	Active compound
15	dihydrozeatin	DHZ	D5-tZ	Active compound
16	jasmonoyl-isoleucine	JA-Ile	D6-ABA	Active compound
17	phenylacetic acid	PAA	D5-BA	Active compound
18	benzoic acid	BA	D5-BA	SA metabolism
19	neophaseic acid	NeoPA	D3-PA	ABA metabolism
20	<i>cis</i> -zeatin riboside	cZR	D5-tZR	cZ metabolism
21	<i>trans</i> -zeatin riboside	tZR	D5-tZR	tZ metabolism
22	gibberellin A4	GA4	D3-PA	Active compound
23	phaseic acid	PA	D3-PA	ABA metabolism
24	dihydrozeatin riboside	DHZR	D5-tZR	DHZ metabolism
25	phenylethylamine	PEA	D6-iP9G	PAA metabolism (putative)
26	isopentenyladenine-9-glucoside	iP9G	D6-iP9G	iP metabolism
27	tryptamine	TRA	D4-TRA	MLT precursor, IAA metabolism
28	isopentenyladenine-7-glucoside	iP7G	D6-iP7G	iP metabolism
29	gibberellin A3	GA3	D3-DPA	Active compound
30	dihydrophaseic acid	DPA	D3-DPA	ABA metabolism
31	2-oxo-indole-3-acetic acid	OxIAA	D3-DPA	IAA metabolism
32	<i>cis</i> -zeatin-9-glucoside	cZ9G	D5-tZ9G	cZ metabolism
33	dihydrozeatin-9-glucoside	DHZ9G	D5-tZ9G	DHZ metabolism
34	<i>trans</i> -zeatin-9-glucoside	tZ9G	D5-tZ9G	tZ metabolism
35	<i>cis</i> -zeatin-7-glucoside and	cZ7G+cZOG	D5-tZ7G	cZ metabolism

	<i>cis</i> -zeatin-O-glucoside (coeluting)			
36	<i>trans</i> -zeatin-7-glucoside	tZ7G	D5-tZ7G	tZ metabolism
37	<i>trans</i> -zeatin-O-glucoside	tZOG	D5-tZOG	cZ metabolism
38	<i>cis</i> -zeatin-O-glucoside riboside	cZROG	D5-tZROG	cZ metabolism
39	<i>trans</i> -zeatin-O-glucoside riboside	tZROG	D5-tZROG	tZ metabolism
40	salicylic acid glucoside	SAG	D3-DPA	SA metabolism
41	indole-3-acetic acid-alanine	IAA-Ala		IAA metabolism
42	indole-3-acetic acid-aspartic acid	IAA-Asp	D5,15N1- IAA-Asp	IAA metabolism
43	indole-3-acetic acid- glutamic acid	IAA-Glu	D5,15N1- IAA-Glu	IAA metabolism
44	serotonin	SRT	D4-SRT	MLT precursor
45	1-aminocyclopropane-1- carboxylic acid	ACC	D4-ACC	Active compound, ethylene precursor
<i>tested but chromatographic separation could not be achieved</i>				
46	isopentenyl adenosine monophosphate	iPMP	-	iP precursor
47	<i>trans</i> -zeatin riboside monophosphate	tZMP	-	tZ precursor
48	<i>cis</i> -zeatin riboside monophosphate	cZMP	-	cZ precursor
49	dihydrozeatin riboside monophosphate	DHZMP	-	DHZ precursor

Tab S2:

A list of analytes' precursor ions, fragments and retention times used in scheduled multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) windows.

IM = ionization mode, CE = collision energy [eV], R_t = retention time [min]

No. in Fig.2	Analyte	Precursor Ion (IM)	Quantifier Ion (CE)	1 st qualifier ion (CE)	2 nd qualifier ion (CE)	R _t Method A5.5	R _t Method B3.0
1	MLT	232.9 (+)	174.0 (-15)	130.1 (-43)	159.1 (-25)	1.702	1.718
2	IAM	175.0 (+)	130.15 (-16)	77.1 (-43)	103.1 (-32)	1.941	1.989
3	OPDA	291.3 (-)	165.35 (20)	247.4 (19)	273.35 (18)	2.135	-
4	SA	137.2 (-)	93.05 (21)	65.0 (29)	-	2.162	-
5	iP	204.1 (+)	136.0 (-15)	119.1 (-30)	148.1 (-13)	2.722	3.927
6	iPR	336.3 (+)	204.2 (-20)	136.05 (-30)	148.0 (-24)	3.084	3.251
7	IBA	203.95 (+)	186.1 (-12)	130.1 (-24)	-	3.124	-
8	JA	209.35 (-)	59.0 (14)	40.9 (37)	-	3.253	-
9	PPyA	163.0 (-)	91.1 (11)	-	-	3.357	-
10	ABA	263.2 (-)	153.2 (13)	204.2 (21)	219.2 (14)	4.517	-
11	ABA-GE	425.1 (-)	153.2 (22)	219.2 (26)	204.2 (32)	4.949	4.804
12	cZ	220.1 (+)	136.15 (-17)	119.05 (-31)	202.15 (-11)	4.968	5.664
13	tZ	220.1 (+)	136.15 (-17)	119.05 (-31)	202.15 (-11)	5.425	5.984
14	IAA	176.0 (+)	130.05 (-16)	77.2 (-42)	103.15 (32)	5.485	-
		174.0 (-)	130.1 (14)	128.15 (15)	-		
15	DHZ	222.1 (+)	136.15 (-21)	148.15 (-21)	119.05 (-35)	5.412	6.137
16	JA-Ile	322.15 (-)	130.2 (22)	128.15 (21)	172.2 (18)	5.449	-
17	PAA	135.1 (-)	91.1 (11)	-	-	5.525	-
18	BA	121.2 (-)	77.0 (15)	-	-	5.567	-
19	NeoPA	279.0 (-)	205.3 (15)	122.1 (29)	235.2 (12)	5.584	-
20	cZR	352.1 (+)	220.2 (-18)	136.05 (-33)	119.0 (-53)	5.564	5.520
21	tZR	352.1 (+)	220.2 (-18)	136.05 (-33)	119.0 (-53)	5.802	5.710
22	GA4	331.2 (-)	257.1 (25)	287.2 (17)	213.3 (31)	5.691	-
23	PA	279.0 (-)	139.15 (16)	205.25 (15)	187.15 (20)	5.729	-
24	DHZR	353.7 (+)	222.2 (-21)	136.1 (-35)	148.0 (-36)	5.742	5.744
25	PEA	122.0 (+)	104.95 (-15)	77.15 (-29)	79.1 (-23)	6.494	7.787
26	iP9G	365.8 (+)	136.05 (-32)	204.2 (-21)	148.15 (-27)	6.702	6.381
27	TRA	160.9 (+)	144.2 (-13)	115.0 (-33)	117.1 (-25)	6.810	7.816
28	iP7G	365.8 (+)	136.05 (-32)	204.2 (-21)	148.15 (-27)	7.237	7.227
29	GA3	345.1 (-)	239.3 (16)	143.2 (30)	221.3 (24)	7.561	3.171
30	DPA	281.0 (-)	237.3 (15)	171.3 (19)	123.05 (19)	7.903	2.872
31	OxIAA	190.0 (-)	146.2 (16)	131.1 (25)	144.1 (23)	8.164	2.793
		191.9 (+)	146.25 (-14)	128.0 (-24)	77.1 (-44)		
32	cZ9G	382.1 (+)	220.0 (-21)	136.15 (-33)	202.1 (-24)	8.494	7.731
33	DHZ9G	383.8 (+)	222.2 (-21)	136.0 (-37)	148.15 (-38)	8.714	7.921
34	tZ9G	382.1 (+)	220.0 (-21)	136.15 (-33)	202.1 (-24)	8.796	7.949
35	cZ7G+ cZOG	382.1 (+)	220.0 (-21)	136.15 (-33)	202.1 (-24)	9.001	8.125
36	tZ7G	382.1 (+)	220.0 (-21)	136.15 (-33)	202.1 (-24)	9.247	8.312
37	tZOG	382.1 (+)	202.1 (-24)	220.0 (-21)	136.15 (-33)	9.499	8.444

38	cZROG	514.2 (+)	382.2 (-20)	220.2 (-27)	202.2 (-32)	9.511	8.418
39	tZROG	514.2 (+)	382.2 (-20)	220.2 (-27)	202.2 (-32)	9.889	8.734
40	SAG	298.7 (-)	137.1 (12)	93.1 (38)	-	10.141	8.874
41	IAA-Ala	247.0 (+)	130.2 (-22)	90.1 (-11)	77.1 (-55)	-	3.303
42	IAA-Asp	291.2 (+)	130.2 (-23)	134.1 (-11)	103.5 (-51)	-	5.004
43	IAA-Glu	305.2 (+)	130.1 (-25)	148.1 (-13)	103.5 (-53)	-	6.721
44	SRT	177.2 (+)	160.1 (-13)	115.1 (-27)	117.1 (-28)	-	8.118
45	ACC	102.2 (+)	56.1 (-12)	28.15 (-23)	-	-	10.806
-	D4-MLT	237.1 (+)	178.2 (-15)	177.2 (-14)	134.1 (-39)	1.704	1.720
-	D6-iPR	342.1 (+)	210.2 (-19)	137.15 (-30)	148.05 (-25)	3.082	3.258
-	D4-SA	141.2 (-)	97.1 (21)	69.1 (31)	-	2.187	-
-	D6-iP	210.1 (+)	137.05 (-15)	75.1 (-22)	148.1 (-13)	2.721	3.937
-	D5-JA	214.3 (-)	61.95 (13)	42.05 (40)	-	3.214	-
-	D6-ABA	269.25 (-)	159.25 (12)	225.25 (15)	207.2 (22)	4.534	-
-	15N4-cZ	224.2 (+)	140.05 (-15)	43.0 (-23)	122.1 (-34)	5.009	5.679
-	D5-tZ	225.1 (+)	137.15 (-15)	118.95 (-33)	207.2 (-12)	5.447	6.007
-	13C6-IAA	182.05 (+) 179.9 (-)	136.05 (-16) 136.2 (14)	109.1 (-31) 134.2 (22)	81.1 (-43) -	5.476	-
-	D5-BA	126.35 (-)	82.1 (14)	-	-	5.574	-
-	D3-PA	282.0 (-)	142.25 (16)	208.15 (16)	171.3 (16)	5.803	-
-	D5-tZR	357.1 (+)	225.2 (-19)	137.05 (-32)	136.05 (-40)	5.828	5.727
-	D6-iP9G	371.8 (+)	137.1 (-32)	210.25 (-21)	147.95 (-27)	6.709	6.385
-	D4-TRA	164.9 (+)	148.1 (-13)	118.1 (-33)	119.0 (-33)	6.836	8.128
-	D6-iP7G	371.8 (+)	137.1 (-32)	210.25 (-21)	147.95 (-27)	7.242	7.236
-	D3-DPA	284.05 (-)	240.25 (16)	174.25 (21)	183.1 (17)	7.922	2.887
-	D5-tZ9G	387.1 (+)	225.2 (-22)	137.15 (-33)	207.0 (-26)	8.822	7.967
-	D5-tZ7G	387.1 (+)	225.2 (-22)	137.15 (-33)	207.0 (-26)	9.269	8.328
-	D5-tZOG	387.1 (+)	207.0 (-26)	225.2 (-22)	137.15 (-33)	9.529	8.463
-	D5-tZROG	519.05 (+)	387.15 (-20)	225.25 (-28)	207.25 (-31)	9.904	8.745
-	D5,15N1- IAA-Asp	297.2 (+)	134.2 (-23)	135.2 (-21)	107.0 (-53)	-	5.025
-	D5,15N1- IAA-Glu	311.1 (+)	134.1 (-21)	135.2 (-25)	107.0 (-55)	-	6.720
-	D4-SRT	180.9 (+)	164.1 (-12)	118.1 (-31)	119.1 (-30)	-	8.121
-	D4-ACC	106.0 (+)	60.15 (-13)	32.2 (-36)	88.0 (-11)	-	10.802

Tab S3:

Lower and upper limits of quantification (LLOQ, ULOQ) of both methods. LLOQ was set as a calibration point for which the error of back-calculated concentration remained within $\pm 20\%$ of the nominal concentration. ULOQ was calibration point with the highest concentration. All analytes were split into 5 groups based on ULOQ, from 10^{-9} to 10^{-13} mol on injection.

No. in Fig.2	Analyte (ionization mode)	Method A5.5		Method B3.0	
		LLOQ [mol/injection]	ULOQ [mol/injection]	LLOQ [mol/injection]	ULOQ [mol/injection]
1	MLT	10^{-15}	10^{-12}	3×10^{-15}	10^{-12}
2	IAM	10^{-15}	10^{-11}	10^{-15}	10^{-11}
3	OPDA	10^{-14}	10^{-12}	-	-
4	SA	3×10^{-14}	10^{-11}	-	-
5	iP	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}
6	iPR	3×10^{-17}	10^{-13}	3×10^{-17}	10^{-13}
7	IBA	10^{-13}	10^{-11}	-	-
8	JA	3×10^{-14}	10^{-10}	-	-
9	PPyA	10^{-12}	10^{-11}	-	-
10	ABA	10^{-15}	10^{-11}	-	-
11	ABA-GE	10^{-14}	10^{-12}	3×10^{-14}	10^{-12}
12	cZ	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}
13	tZ	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}
14	IAA (+)	10^{-12}	10^{-10}	-	-
	IAA (-)	3×10^{-13}	10^{-10}	-	-
15	DHZ	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}	10^{-15}	10^{-12}
16	JA-Ile	10^{-15}	10^{-12}	-	-
17	PAA	3×10^{-13}	10^{-9}	-	-
18	BA	3×10^{-12}	10^{-9}	-	-
19	NeoPA	10^{-14}	10^{-12}	-	-
20	cZR	10^{-16}	10^{-13}	3×10^{-17}	10^{-13}
21	tZR	10^{-16}	10^{-13}	3×10^{-17}	10^{-13}
22	GA4	3×10^{-14}	10^{-11}	-	-
23	PA	3×10^{-14}	10^{-12}	-	-
24	DHZR	3×10^{-16}	10^{-13}	3×10^{-16}	10^{-13}
25	PEA	10^{-14}	10^{-11}	3×10^{-14}	10^{-11}
26	iP9G	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}	10^{-16}	10^{-12}
27	TRA	10^{-13}	10^{-11}	3×10^{-15}	10^{-11}
28	iP7G	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}	10^{-16}	10^{-12}
29	GA3	3×10^{-14}	10^{-11}	10^{-14}	10^{-11}
30	DPA	10^{-13}	10^{-12}	3×10^{-14}	10^{-12}
31	OxIAA(-)	10^{-13}	10^{-12}	-	-
	OxIAA(+)	-	-	10^{-15}	10^{-12}

32	cZ9G	10^{-16}	10^{-12}	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}
33	DHZ9G			3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}
34	tZ9G	10^{-16}	10^{-12}	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}
35	cZ7G+cZOG	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}
36	tZ7G	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}	3×10^{-16}	10^{-12}
37	tZOG	3×10^{-14}	10^{-12}	3×10^{-15}	10^{-12}
38	cZROG	10^{-13}	10^{-12}	3×10^{-15}	10^{-12}
39	tZROG	10^{-13}	10^{-12}	3×10^{-15}	10^{-12}
40	SAG	10^{-12}	10^{-11}	3×10^{-14}	10^{-11}
41	IAA-Ala	-	-	3×10^{-16}	10^{-13}
42	IAA-Asp	-	-	3×10^{-14}	10^{-11}
43	IAA-Glu	-	-	3×10^{-14}	10^{-11}
44	SRT	-	-	3×10^{-13}	10^{-11}
45	ACC	-	-	3×10^{-12}	10^{-9}

Tab S4:

Accuracy of MethodA5.5 and MethodB3.0 assessed by spiking real samples at three different concentration levels (High:Mid:Low in concentration ratio 10:3:1) (n=3).

Analyte	Internal standard	High		Mid		Low	
		MethodA5.5	MethodB3.0	MethodA5.5	MethodB3.0	MethodA5.5	MethodB3.0
MLT	D4-MLT	-	-8.39 ± 3.1 %	-	-0.81 ± 3.81 %	-	-2.25 ± 9.18 %
SA	D4-SA	2.33 ± 6.06 %	-	-4.02 ± 2.89 %	-	*	-
iP	D6-iP	-0.08 ± 3.41 %	0.61 ± 6.66 %	2.83 ± 3.84 %	7.04 ± 3.44 %	-2.05 ± 3.84 %	6.91 ± 6.18 %
iPR	D6-iPR	-3.88 ± 3.12 %	-1.12 ± 5.25 %	-0.43 ± 2.37 %	-1.69 ± 2.22 %	0.85 ± 2.25 %	1.92 ± 3.93 %
JA	D5-JA	7.26 ± 3.62 %	-	1.28 ± 11.83 %	-	0.52 ± 10.66 %	-
ABA	D6-ABA	3.58 ± 2.56 %	-	2.95 ± 1.89 %	-	-2.44 ± 3.34 %	-
cZ	15N4-cZ	-4.04 ± 11.93 %	-7.54 ± 2.36 %	2.24 ± 9.44 %	6.58 ± 6.41 %	0.97 ± 10.46 %	3.6 ± 2.79 %
tZ	D5-tZ	-1.01 ± 6.01 %	9.9 ± 0.46 %	-1.66 ± 2.62 %	13.49 ± 0.68 %	-3.2 ± 1.66 %	2.3 ± 5.88 %
IAA	13C6-IAA	2.51 ± 6.04 %	-	-0.15 ± 6.75 %	-	-0.76 ± 8.44 %	-
BA	D5-BA	6.02 ± 5.57 %	-	13.2 ± 2.52 %	-	-2.13 ± 9.03 %	-
tZR	D5-tZR	4.17 ± 7.85 %	5.97 ± 4.48 %	1.17 ± 11.05 %	-1.58 ± 10.43 %	4.12 ± 1.43 %	4.86 ± 8.3 %
PA	D3-PA	5.34 ± 7.36 %	-	-7.95 ± 7.89 %	-	-6.36 ± 4.21 %	-
iP9G	D6-iP9G	1.68 ± 1.99 %	4.13 ± 2.75 %	-1.59 ± 1.86 %	7.04 ± 2.84 %	-0.44 ± 2.23 %	5.81 ± 4.32 %
iP7G	D6-iP7G	-3.17 ± 4.67 %	3.27 ± 1.27 %	-8.1 ± 3.09 %	4.7 ± 2.49 %	0.88 ± 7.65 %	5.28 ± 5.75 %
TRA	D4-TRA	8.42 ± 4.21 %	-	7.75 ± 4.56 %	-	3.21 ± 5.62 %	-
DPA	D3-DPA	1.8 ± 9.28 %	-	8.3 ± 2.34 %	-	**	-
tZ9G	D5-tZ9G	0.51 ± 5.73 %	-5.16 ± 2.03 %	-4.54 ± 2.73 %	-6.83 ± 1.65 %	5.68 ± 3.67 %	-5.13 ± 5.22 %
tZ7G	D5-tZ7G	-1.78 ± 3.16 %	-2.5 ± 3.35 %	6.89 ± 4.08 %	-0.22 ± 5.01 %	6.73 ± 5.24 %	3.57 ± 8.3 %
tZOG	D5-tZOG	-4.7 ± 2.69 %	-3.74 ± 4.84 %	-0.74 ± 3.06 %	-4.52 ± 8.43 %	14.06 ± 2.07 %	0.75 ± 6.6 %

tZROG	D5-tZROG	2.41 ± 4.85 %	2.01 ± 5.78 %	-4.87 ± 6.58 %	-5.65 ± 7.68 %	2.72 ± 5.72 %	1.41 ± 8 %
ACC	D4-ACC	-	3.22 ± 2.47 %	-	-2.19 ± 10.47 %	-	-1.33 ± 11.02%

* = covered by high endogenous content

** = below LOQ

Tab S5:

Relative standard deviations of repeated measurements to assess intra-day and inter-day precision of Method A5.5 and Method B3.0.

Analyte	Method A5.5		Method B3.0	
	Intra-day precision	Inter-day precision	Intra-day precision	Inter-day precision
MLT	5.6 %	13.4 %	3.7 %	3.7 %
IAM	2.3 %	1.1 %	5.4 %	2.9 %
OPDA	4.3 %	4.8 %	-	-
SA	5.5 %	10.4 %	-	-
iP	8.2 %	7.3 %	9.9 %	5.1 %
iPR	7.5 %	3.9 %	4.0 %	6.2 %
IBA	5.2 %	9.6 %	-	-
JA	6.7 %	4.7 %	-	-
ABA	3.2 %	1.2 %	-	-
ABA-GE*	13.8 %	14.3 %	11.7 %	9.0 %
cZ	7.0 %	6.7 %	-	-
tZ	5.9 %	4.0 %	-	-
IAA	11.6 %	8.0 %	-	-
DHZ*	5.7 %	10.9 %	-	-
JA-Ile	4.6 %	5.6 %	-	-
PAA	7.0 %	1.3 %	-	-
BA	5.4 %	11.0 %	-	-
NeoPA	4.9 %	11.8 %	-	-
cZR	10.1 %	4.7 %	4.4 %	14.2 %
tZR	8.4 %	6.6 %	13.5 %	11.6 %
GA4*	-	-	-	-
PA*	9.1 %	4.0 %	-	-
DHZR	4.2 %	10.0 %	7.2 %	1.9 %
PEA	8.9 %	8.9 %	6.8 %	5.8 %
iP9G	3.4 %	4.2 %	2.3 %	4.7 %
iP7G	3.7 %	2.4 %	2.6 %	0.7 %
TRA	2.9 %	5.3 %	3.9 %	8.4 %
GA3*	2.7 %	6.1 %	-	-
DPA	15.0 %	3.9 %	-	-
OxIAA	7.3 %	9.1 %	8.0 %	14.1 %
cZ9G*	5.9 %	11.8 %	13.5 %	12.5 %
tZ9G	7.6 %	4.4 %	6.8 %	9.1 %
cZ7G+cZOG	6.9 %	5.7 %	8.4 %	4.4 %
tZ7G	3.1 %	2.7 %	8.1 %	7.1 %
tZOG	8.1 %	11.6 %	14.7 %	4.7 %
DHZ9G*	-	-	15.0 %	5.6 %
cZROG	5.0 %	16.8 %	13.3 %	13.0 %
tZROG*	4.5 %	13.1 %	11.7 %	10.3 %
SAG	8.0 %	11.8 %	3.8 %	5.8 %

ACC	-	-	7.2 %	0.8 %
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* = spiked due to the absence in tested real sample

Tab S6:

Method process efficiency (PE). PE was calculated as a ratio of peak area of internal standards in real samples (pre-extraction addition) to peak area in standard solution. Three different amounts of sample material (*Arabidopsis* leaves) were tested (n = 3).

Method	Internal standard (ionization mode)	1,2 mg DW (20 mg FW equiv.)	2,4 mg DW (40 mg FW equiv.)	4,8 mg DW (80 mg FW equiv.)
Method A5.5	(D4) - MLT	20.12 ± 7.13 %	12.13 ± 1.79 %	18.12 ± 3.11 %
	(D4) - SA	38.86 ± 3.59 %	45.65 ± 2.71 %	32.34 ± 1.6 %
	(D6) - iP	81.06 ± 25.27 %	117.55 ± 13.73 %	116.96 ± 2.75 %
	(D6) - iPR	110.67 ± 21.14 %	137.02 ± 13.27 %	144.93 ± 3.88 %
	(D5) - JA	13.33 ± 0.47 %	11.56 ± 2.01 %	4.94 ± 0.18 %
	(D6) - ABA	70.28 ± 18.78 %	88.25 ± 11.4 %	66.9 ± 1.79 %
	(D5) - tZ	76.35 ± 12.36 %	105.37 ± 6.78 %	134.67 ± 5.01 %
	(15N4) - cZ	83.3 ± 21.86 %	92.85 ± 8.03 %	97.09 ± 1.38 %
	(13C6) - IAA (+)	205.56 ± 45.96 %	275.44 ± 41.66 %	406.21 ± 20.41 %
	(13C6) - IAA (-)	1,042.55 ± 10.65 %	1,346.29 ± 91.82 %	1,575.11 ± 47.05 %
	(D5) - BA	90.04 ± 14.19 %	116.77 ± 2.96 %	96.47 ± 3.16 %
	(D5) - tZR	30.62 ± 5.4 %	41.38 ± 7 %	70.39 ± 6.46 %
	(D3) - PA	74.75 ± 27.67 %	46.62 ± 1.9 %	13.31 ± 1.43 %
	(D6) - iP9G	92.41 ± 20.47 %	103.61 ± 8.98 %	104 ± 4.24 %
	(D6) - iP7G	20.32 ± 6.06 %	24.39 ± 3.44 %	23.03 ± 0.49 %
	(D4) - TRA	923.58 ± 15.19 %	1038.76 ± 154.57 %	2023.92 ± 37.2 %
	(D3) - DPA	94 ± 23.53 %	109.8 ± 11.84 %	136.51 ± 9.84 %
	(D5) - tZ9G	151.92 ± 33.12 %	130.3 ± 7.41 %	111.36 ± 5.9 %
	(D5) - tZ7G	177.27 ± 50.23 %	159.48 ± 13.98 %	188.45 ± 9.01 %
	(D5) - tZOG	109.92 ± 18.47 %	91.71 ± 5.19 %	81.17 ± 4.26 %
(D5) - tZROG	2,988.92 ± 249.82 %	1,863.05 ± 96.49 %	2,383.44 ± 126.99 %	
Method B3.0	(D4) - MLT	17.02 ± 3.14 %	18.66 ± 3.39 %	21.03 ± 0.83 %
	(D6) - iPR	117.69 ± 29.09 %	115.17 ± 10.09 %	99.27 ± 3.44 %
	(D6) - iP	85.89 ± 18.84 %	75.43 ± 4.55 %	52.95 ± 0.89 %
	(D5) - tZR	7.88 ± 1.55 %	6.25 ± 0.78 %	6.98 ± 0.53 %
	(D5) - tZ	28.37 ± 6.55 %	25.29 ± 3.13 %	24.00 ± 1.09 %
	(15N4) - cZ	3.07 ± 0.63 %	3.99 ± 0.41 %	7.38 ± 1.83 %
	(D6) - iP9G	47.71 ± 11.61 %	45.07 ± 2.48 %	44.14 ± 1.32 %
	(D6) - iP7G	57.07 ± 15.22 %	52.85 ± 3.41 %	42.92 ± 0.69 %
	(D4) - TRA	28.94 ± 8.8 %	27.98 ± 2.98 %	35.31 ± 3.97 %
	(D5) - tZ9G	23.39 ± 5.60 %	20.42 ± 1.23 %	15.58 ± 0.52 %
	(D5) - tZ7G	134.62 ± 34.07 %	105.04 ± 8.7 %	102.48 ± 1.86 %
	(D5) - tZOG	119.77 ± 30.95 %	80.74 ± 9.69 %	92.1 ± 5.98 %
	(D5) - tZROG	107.43 ± 20.01 %	62.51 ± 5.64 %	50.97 ± 1.64 %
(D4) - ACC	217.29 ± 36.85 %	90.59 ± 12.3 %	82.74 ± 3.81 %	

Tab. S7:

Measured concentration of various analytes [pmol/g DW; unless specified], plant weight, dry content and mortality of Col-0 *Arabidopsis* seedlings under control conditions and 3 treatments: nutrient deficiency – 1/3 MS, salinity – NaCl, and combined 1/3MS_NaCl.

Variable	Col-0_MS	Col-0_1/3MS	Col-0_NaCl	Col-0_1/3MS_NaCl	Method used to acquire data
PlantWeight DW [mg]	2.63	1.56	1.05	0.91	HILIC independent
DryContent	8.98 %	6.82 %	12.14 %	7.76 %	
Mortality	2.38 %	3.57 %	1.19 %	8.33 %	
IAM	50.5 ± 7.5	31.6 ± 12.7	55.5 ± 24.1	16.6 ± 7.2	Method A5.5
SA (nmol/g DW)	36.9 ± 9.8	45.2 ± 10.1	34.7 ± 3.6	45.3 ± 10.4	
iP	2.8 ± 0.5	2.8 ± 0.4	2.6 ± 0.2	1.9 ± 0.3	
iPR	38.0 ± 4.4	25.7 ± 0.4	29.1 ± 1.9	17.6 ± 0.7	
JA					
ABA	881.2 ± 82.2	393.9 ± 51.1	1,275.5 ± 79.4	1,048.3 ± 18.9	
ABA-GE	52.6 ± 4.9		109.9 ± 0.4		
cZ	6.8 ± 2.4	4.9 ± 1.6	8.9 ± 4.7	8.2 ± 1.7	
tZ	6.5 ± 0.9	4.5 ± 0.8	3.7 ± 1.6		
IAA (nmol/g DW)	1.7 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.3			
JA-Ile	33.9 ± 17.3	97.0 ± 26.8		94.8 ± 8.5	
PAA (nmol/g DW)	54.8 ± 21.2	83.4 ± 18.3	53.1 ± 10.4	44.5 ± 9.1	
BA (μmol/g DW)	15.1 ± 5.4	18.2 ± 2.0	12.6 ± 0.9	22.1 ± 9.6	
cZR	5.7 ± 1.3	7.1 ± 1.5	10.1 ± 1.0	12.4 ± 1.6	
tZR	44.3 ± 4.4	33.9 ± 4.2	30.4 ± 4.0	12.9 ± 0.8	
PA (nmol/g DW)	4.3 ± 0.5	1.3 ± 0.4	10.4 ± 2.8	3.4 ± 0.5	
DHZR					
PEA (nmol/g DW)	2.6 ± 0.5	2.8 ± 0.9	12.2 ± 2.8	6.2 ± 0.2	
iP9G	20.3 ± 1.7	29.8 ± 1.4	22.7 ± 1.9	36.1 ± 0.5	

iP7G	359.1 ± 10.7	542.6 ± 20.9	465.9 ± 18.7	640.4 ± 12.8
DPA (nmol/g DW)	1.7 ± 0.2		2.3 ± 0.5	0.7 ± 0.1
tZ9G	49.2 ± 2.5	66.3 ± 1.8	44.6 ± 3.2	38.1 ± 2.0
cZ7G+cZOG	130.1 ± 13.3	208.0 ± 26.1	227.7 ± 19.9	347.5 ± 27.8
tZ7G	146.7 ± 10.5	202.0 ± 9.6	164.1 ± 4.4	121.6 ± 3.5
MLT	13.5 ± 0.8	19.0 ± 2.1	33.9 ± 5.9	41.7 ± 5.1
OxIAA	459.8 ± 6.1	361.9 ± 105.4	254.6 ± 52.6	87.1 ± 16.2
tZOG	136.6 ± 45.0	285.9 ± 55.1	95.6 ± 12.0	77.3 ± 15.9
cZROG	44.7 ± 10.0	33.4 ± 11.4	40.7 ± 7.5	56.5 ± 11.3
SAG (nmol/g DW)	26.1 ± 9.6	19.4 ± 5.7	39.3 ± 4.0	15.9 ± 2.9
ACC (nmol/g DW)	52.5 ± 3.3	49.2 ± 13.2	70.9 ± 13.4	44.9 ± 7.1

Method B3.0

Tab. S8:

Measured concentration of various analytes [pmol/g DW; unless specified], plant weight, dry content and mortality of Ler *Arabidopsis* seedlings under control conditions and 3 treatments: nutrient deficiency – 1/3 MS, salinity – NaCl, and combined 1/3MS_NaCl.

Variable	Ler_MS	Ler_1/3MS	Ler_NaCl	Ler_1/3MS_NaCl	Method used to acquire data
PlantWeight DW [mg]	2.10	0.87	0.95	1.00	HILJC independent
DryContent	9.13 %	4.56 %	13.38 %	9.92 %	
Mortality	3.57 %	10.71 %	4.76 %	21.43 %	
IAM	42.4 ± 13.9	43.3 ± 18.3	156.9 ± 61.9	59.6 ± 18.6	Method A.5.5
SA (nmol/g DW)	53.0 ± 16.2	24.3 ± 2.7	49.4 ± 6.1	53.7 ± 13.6	
iP	0.8 ± 0.2	2.0 ± 0.5	3.8 ± 0.4	2.3 ± 0.3	
iPR	47.9 ± 3.7	15.0 ± 1.5	39.5 ± 0.9	18.3 ± 2.7	
JA				565.5 ± 132.9	
ABA	1,180.8 ± 170.8	195.2 ± 28.6	1,460.1 ± 44.1	1,099.0 ± 55.8	
ABA-GE			263.7 ± 41.5	140.2 ± 41.2	
cZ		8.5 ± 1.3		6.8 ± 2.6	
tZ	5.1 ± 0.9		1.6 ± 0.3		
IAA (nmol/g DW)	1.7 ± 0.6	1.4 ± 0.2			
JA-Ile			225.5 ± 28.0	507.2 ± 48.5	
PAA (nmol/g DW)	108.9 ± 24.0	40.6 ± 7.3	30.6 ± 2.2	34.0 ± 2.8	
BA (µmol/g DW)	30.4 ± 11.1	31.2 ± 16.2	11.3 ± 0.9	16.7 ± 5.3	
cZR	12.1 ± 2.2	17.4 ± 3.1	4.9 ± 0.5	5.6 ± 0.5	
tZR	33.4 ± 3.2	8.2 ± 0.8	27.9 ± 1.1	16.0 ± 1.9	
PA (nmol/g DW)	5.6 ± 0.3	1.0 ± 0.2	8.8 ± 0.6	6.0 ± 1.3	
DHZR					
PEA (nmol/g DW)	0.4 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.2	2.5 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.1	
iP9G	18.4 ± 0.3	28.9 ± 0.5	22.5 ± 0.6	25.1 ± 0.9	

iP7G	375.5 ± 5.4	566.2 ± 16.9	479.0 ± 3.3	521.1 ± 2.8
DPA (nmol/g DW)	1.2 ± 0.1		1.4 ± 0.3	
tZ9G	61.1 ± 1.7	35.6 ± 0.8	47.8 ± 2.9	58.6 ± 2.0
cZ7G+cZOG	125.5 ± 18.4	451.6 ± 66.6	176.1 ± 5.2	302.7 ± 18.3
tZ7G	175.7 ± 5.6	92.5 ± 5.9	163.8 ± 6.6	175.3 ± 4.4
MLT	13.7 ± 1.0	26.0 ± 1.4	26.4 ± 1.1	41.6 ± 6.3
OxIAA	221.7 ± 17.7	113.4 ± 21.8	171.3 ± 11.5	75.3 ± 12.2
tZOG	42.1 ± 8.1	59.9 ± 3.3	37.7 ± 3.9	70.2 ± 12.8
cZROG	40.6 ± 11.7	66.1 ± 15.2	66.7 ± 5.4	79.0 ± 3.1
SAG (nmol/g DW)	28.7 ± 5.4	10.1 ± 2.6	50.5 ± 4.4	56.9 ± 0.8
ACC (nmol/g DW)	40.4 ± 9.3	29.7 ± 4.6	54.4 ± 9.8	37.2 ± 4.3

Method B3.0

Tab. S9:

Measured concentration of various analytes [pmol/g DW; unless specified], plant weight, dry content and mortality of WS-2 *Arabidopsis* seedlings under control conditions and 3 treatments: nutrient deficiency – 1/3 MS, salinity – NaCl, and combined 1/3MS_NaCl.

Variable	WS-2_MS	WS-2_1/3MS	WS-2_NaCl	WS-2_1/3MS_NaCl	Method used to acquire data
PlantWeight DW [mg]	2.53	1.15	1.05	1.00	HILJC independent
DryContent	9.30 %	6.78 %	10.86 %	9.42 %	
Mortality	5.95 %	11.90 %	75.00 %	10.71 %	
IAM	74.9 ± 27.3	39.4 ± 13.8	106.2 ± 18.6	60.4 ± 40.9	Method A5.5
SA (nmol/g DW)	37.7 ± 10.9	78.8 ± 5.8	30.8 ± 9.5	61.6 ± 10.0	
iP	4.0 ± 0.8	2.3 ± 0.4	3.4 ± 0.2	2.7 ± 0.1	
iPR	87.9 ± 22.3	29.0 ± 1.3	23.2 ± 2.4	28.1 ± 7.4	
JA					
ABA	1,545.0 ± 137.5	163.9 ± 5.0	1,740.3 ± 179.3	1,774.7 ± 55.3	
ABA-GE	69.0 ± 25.2		352.6 ± 196.1	151.4 ± 5.6	
cZ	4.5 ± 2.3	12.1 ± 2.2		10.1 ± 2.9	
tZ	7.1 ± 2.7	3.7 ± 0.0	3.5 ± 0.0	3.3 ± 1.4	
IAA (nmol/g DW)	1.8 ± 0.6				
JA-Ile	36.2 ± 8.0			144.1 ± 26.2	
PAA (nmol/g DW)	54.0 ± 8.4	47.2 ± 8.8	22.5 ± 3.2	36.8 ± 2.6	
BA (µmol/g DW)	11.2 ± 3.9	31.8 ± 8.6	14.6 ± 6.2	30.3 ± 12.6	
cZR	14.8 ± 3.4	15.7 ± 2.3	4.9 ± 1.3	15.2 ± 4.0	
tZR	65.9 ± 17.4	29.1 ± 3.6	26.2 ± 4.3	40.2 ± 6.4	
PA (nmol/g DW)	8.9 ± 2.2	0.9 ± 0.2	10.8 ± 1.4	7.9 ± 2.1	
DHZR	6.1 ± 2.8	3.7 ± 0.3	4.1 ± 0.7	3.7 ± 1.0	
PEA (nmol/g DW)	0.4 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.4	0.5 ± 0.1	
iP9G	15.5 ± 0.9	17.9 ± 0.3	14.4 ± 0.4	18.0 ± 1.4	

iP7G	291.2 ± 16.2	384.0 ± 15.7	327.2 ± 19.7	384.7 ± 17.0
DPA (nmol/g DW)	1.4 ± 0.1		2.8 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.1
tZ9G	35.5 ± 2.6	52.8 ± 2.0	38.8 ± 2.6	47.3 ± 3.7
cZ7G+cZOG	76.1 ± 9.0	290.9 ± 15.2	98.9 ± 15.5	192.4 ± 49.4
tZ7G	109.0 ± 2.0	146.5 ± 10.3	112.0 ± 6.4	131.1 ± 11.2
MLT	12.0 ± 1.2	22.2 ± 2.4	24.1 ± 2.0	29.9 ± 0.9
OxIAA	264.1 ± 85.7	141.6 ± 13.6	153.7 ± 61.7	61.6 ± 13.3
tZOG	45.5 ± 8.7	95.5 ± 19.3	29.8 ± 1.6	50.3 ± 20.7
cZROG	49.4 ± 5.6	73.0 ± 5.0	40.0 ± 6.1	58.8 ± 5.5
SAG (nmol/g DW)	35.0 ± 3.4	86.1 ± 15.9	18.8 ± 6.1	41.0 ± 10.7
ACC (nmol/g DW)	36.7 ± 9.6	39.9 ± 5.7	73.4 ± 4.4	38.9 ± 4.3

Method B3.0